

Supplemental Materials for “Qualitative and Quantitative Analyses of Noninvasive Diagnosis of Insulinoma Using [¹⁸F]FB(ePEG12)12-exendin-4 PET/CT”

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Supplemental Table 1. Summary of the mean standardized uptake values (SUVmean) according to tumor localization.

	tumor	tumor / pancreas	tumor / liver	tumor / spleen	tumor / left ventricular lumen
Body& Tail	12.44 ± 3.88	9.48 ± 2.09	20.36 ± 6.98	20.57 ± 4.92	13.22 ± 2.95
Head	13.57 ± 4.59	8.48 ± 1.77	27.16 ± 8.26	23.90 ± 5.81	11.44 ± 3.50
p-value	0.86	0.72	0.56	0.67	0.71

Supplemental Table 1 Legend: Analysis of SUVmean (mean ± SD) values and ratio 120 min after [¹⁸F]FB(ePEG12)12-exendin-4 administration according to tumor localization.

Body & Tail; pancreatic body-tail regions, Head; pancreatic head.

Supplemental Table 2. Comparison of the mean standardized uptake values (SUVmean) according to whether or not diazoxide was used.

	tumor	tumor / pancreas	tumor / liver	tumor / spleen	tumor / left ventricular lumen
Diazoxide (-)	17.94 ± 3.73	11.03 ± 1.71	33.81 ± 6.36	28.82 ± 4.53	15.62 ± 3.05
Diazoxide (+)	8.12 ± 4.08	7.30 ± 1.87	12.99 ± 6.97	16.40 ± 4.96	9.43 ± 3.34
p-value	0.11	0.18	0.055	0.18	0.20

Supplemental Table 2 Legend: Analysis of SUVmean (mean ± SD) values and ratio 120 min after [¹⁸F]FB(ePEG12)12-exendin-4 administration.

Supplemental Figure 1. Correlation between the SUVmean in [¹⁸F]FB(ePEG12)12-exendin-4 positron emission tomography/computed tomography (PET/CT) images and body mass index, Fajans index, volume of ¹⁸F-exendin-4, Ki-67 and Tumor size.

Supplemental Figure 1 Legend: Correlation between SUVmean 120 min after [¹⁸F]FB(ePEG12)12-exendin-4 injection and each parameter is shown as “r”. SUVmean vs each parameter, ns; not significant. LV; left ventricular lumen.